

(Perceptions and Utilization of Information and Communication Technology on Service ... Haladu, S. A. Et. al. 2025)

**Perceptions and Utilization of Information and Communication Technology on Service Delivery
among Nigerian Colleges of Aviation Technology Staff**

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Abstract

This paper explores the perceptions and utilization of information and communication technology on service delivery among Nigerian Colleges of Aviation Technology staff. Survey research design was adapted. The population of the study comprises 820 staff members at NCAT Zaria with a sample of 350 participants. Simple Random Sampling Technique was used in selecting and administering the self-developed closed-ended questionnaire. Multiple Regression statistical tool through the aid of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 was used in testing the hypotheses of the study. The Cronbach alpha reliability test revealed performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions and public service delivery have Cronbach coefficient of 0.876; 0.741; 0.909; 0.897; and 0.918 respectively. All the coefficients are more than 0.7 indicating that the instruments are reliable, suitable and fit for the study. The study also adapted the use of face validity by employing the expertise of two public sector professionals and two academics from the Department of Public Administration, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. The result of the analysis revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions and public service delivery in Nigerian College of Aviation Technology Zaria ($p < 0.05$), while there is a positive but insignificant relationship between social influence and public service delivery in Nigerian College of Aviation Technology Zaria ($p > 0.05$). This recommended that NCAT should implement comprehensive training programs for staff on the effective use of ICT tools in delivering services.

Keywords: ICT, aviation education, public service delivery, organizational performance, NCAT

Introduction

Providing high-quality education is a fundamental responsibility of academic institutions, particularly in specialized fields such as aviation. In recent years, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) such as electronic governance, otherwise called e-governance, has become increasingly vital for enhancing educational delivery and organizational performance (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023).

Electronic governance simply refers to the use of ICT in government dealings with a view to providing quality services to its stakeholders (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023). E-governance has improved communication

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between the government and its stakeholders. Today, citizens can easily communicate through electronic mails (i.e., emails), webchats, WhatsApp, Facebooks, LinkedIn and other electronic means (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023; Avazov, & Lee, 2022). Particularly within the academic institution, e-governance has been used to remedy the long awaiting hours by students during registration and payments. Formerly, students usually spent days and weeks trying to register courses and make payments for a particular session, queuing to be attended to, thereby wasting valuable time that could have been spent reading or doing one assignment or another.

Previously, citizens have to visit government establishments before making registrations or payments, however, with the aid of e-governance. Students can now register for courses and also make payments for school fees among others. E-governance has brought all these services at their fingertips. In other words, e-governance has made students' online registration and payment more cost-effective, faster, easier, affordable, available and also enhanced (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023).

The Nigerian College of Aviation Technology (NCAT) serves as a critical institution for training professionals in the aviation sector. This paper seeks to assess the influence of ICT utilization on public service delivery at NCAT, addressing the challenges and opportunities presented by digital technologies.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the huge investments and the acknowledged potential of ICT, optimizing its actual utilization and realizing its full benefits within Nigerian public sector institutions, including educational bodies like NCATs, remains a significant challenge (Asogwa, 2013; Obisesan & Lawal, 2024). Numerous studies highlight common barriers to effective ICT adoption in Nigeria, such as inadequate infrastructure, limited digital literacy, affordability issues, and insufficient maintenance and support (Njoku, Ozurumba, Ubah, Nwaimo, Ugwu, Akujor, Ejiogu, Nwoko, 2024; Adebayo & Bakare, 2023). Specifically, digital transformation within the Nigerian aviation industry has been characterized as slow and problematic, leading to inefficiencies, outdated processes, and suboptimal service delivery (Opuala-Charles, 2025; Ilesanmi & Adeosun, 2024).

The effective utilization of ICT by staff is fundamentally dependent on their perceptions and acceptance of these technologies (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Al-Hujran et al., 2020). Research in Nigeria indicates that even with increased access, key factors influencing user acceptance – namely Performance Expectancy (perceived job benefits), Effort Expectancy (perceived ease of use), Social Influence (peer and organizational encouragement), and Facilitating Conditions (availability of resources and support) – are not consistently optimal and vary considerably across institutions and user groups (Achugbue & Okuonghae, 2024; Ojo, 2025; Bello & Ajayi, 2023). For instance, while some studies show moderate agreement on ease of use and support availability, the perception of social influence is highly variable (Achugbue & Okuonghae, 2024; Danjuma & Lawal, 2024). This divergence in perceptions often leads to the underutilization of expensive ICT systems, poor integration into daily workflows, and ultimately, a failure to significantly enhance service efficiency and quality.

Therefore, despite the strategic importance of ICT and ongoing efforts to digitize public services, there's an inadequate understanding of how NCAT staff's perceptions of Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence, and Facilitating Conditions specifically influence their utilization of ICT and, subsequently, the quality of public service delivery within these institutions. Without addressing these

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critical perceptual and utilization gaps, the transformative potential of ICT in supporting Nigeria's aviation training and regulatory mandate may remain unrealized, potentially hindering operational efficiency, staff productivity, and overall institutional effectiveness (Opuala-Charles, 2025; Umar & Musa, 2024).

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to assess the perceptions and utilization of information and communication technology on service delivery among Nigerian Colleges of Aviation Technology staff. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine the effect of performance expectancy on public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.
2. Ascertain the effect of effort expectancy on public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.
3. Determine the effect of social influence on public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.
4. Assess the effect of facilitating conditions on public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised by the study:

1. To what extent does performance expectancy affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?
2. To what extent does effort expectancy affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?
3. To what extent does social influence affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?
4. To what extent does facilitating conditions affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were developed to guide the study:

1. Performance expectancy does not significantly affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.
2. Effort expectancy does not significantly affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.
3. Social influence does not significantly affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.
4. Facilitating conditions do not significantly affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria.

Literature Review

The significance of ICT in education has been widely documented, emphasizing its potential to improve operational efficiencies and service delivery (Dike, 2018; Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023). E-governance, which integrates ICT into public administration, has emerged as a tool for enhancing transparency, accountability, and efficiency in service delivery (Zheng et al., 2022).

There is no doubt that service delivery is defined by several scholars to reflect their perceptions and ideology. Akpan, Dung, and Ibegbulam (2020) define service delivery as the direct and indirect services that a government offers to its citizens or residents of a nation. The writers went on to say that the government can directly serve the public by producing, distributing, or providing services, as well as indirectly by funding services that are provided to the public by outside organizations. Service delivery, according to Ndema (2022), is the process of attending to residents' demands through timely and effective procedures. The primary responsibility of any government is to deliver public services at affordable or lower cost. Nwekeaku and Obiorah (2019) supported this by arguing that the government's main duty is to provide citizens with services through its public service in an efficient, timely, and cost-effective manner,

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especially now that the nation is under civil rule after the democratic wave that has swept through the world.

Public service was defined by Chukwuemeka, Okeke, and Onwuchekwa (2018) as the direct and indirect services that the government provide to its citizens or residents of a nation. They went on to say that the government serves the public directly by producing, distributing, or providing services, and indirectly by funding services that are provided to the public by outside parties. Good roads, security, portable water, a good healthcare system, and high-quality education are all part of it. Similarly, to this, Badmus (2017) service delivery is described as basic services provided by the government such as social amenities like hospitals, roads, electricity, water supply, marketplace, customs services, licensing, sanitary services, physical infrastructure, town planning, and housing among others.

According to Olalekan and Oludare (2017), service delivery is the provision of services of public interest to citizens. One of the most important connections between the governed and the government is the provision of services. The provision of social amenities and other services to the general public is known as service delivery. Onwunyi and Okoli (2017) state that in order to accomplish an organization's objectives, service delivery entails carrying out the obligations and responsibilities delegated by established authorities that one has committed to. The entirety of the facilities or amenities that the government offers to the general public is referred to as public service. Agba, Ochimana and Abubakar (2013) defined public service as the activities of government employees and institutions aimed at formulating and implementing governmental policies and programmes for the interests of the masses (public). The low standard of life around the nation makes the pursuit of high-quality service delivery essential.

Within the context of this paper, public service delivery simply refers to the ability of Nigerian College of Aviation Technology (NCAT) to easily and affordably provide services such as students' online registration and payment.

Concept of Electronic Governance

The concept of e-governance can be defined as the adoption of ICT to enhance the working of the government (Obike, 2022). According to Ali, (2023), E-governance is adopting the use of technology in an effective, efficient manner in the exercise of economic, political, administrative, and social management of public affairs by involving the citizens in public policy making. The intentional and methodical use of computer networks and ICT resources to support successful and efficient public service delivery is known as e-governance (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023). According to Oghuvbu, Gberevbie, and Oni (2022), e-governance is essentially the application of ICTs in government business processes. The authors added that the main goal of e-government is to make citizen interaction with the government more convenient and simpler. Dahiru, Yusuf and Yerima (2022) further defined e-governance as the process of improving government processes through the use of technology for automation and harmonization of government activities. It is a contemporary method of overseeing and enhancing the public service process, the authors added. To Umar and Ikechukwu (2022) e-governance is an enablement or a key instrument that allows effective service delivery to the public through the adoption of ICT.

Hartanto, Dalle, Akrim and Anisah (2021) noted that e-governance encompasses the utilization of information and communication technologies to accelerate the collaboration among the government and

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citizens to promote accountability and improve service delivery. It is the use of electronic devices to execute government activities. According to Ezeobebe, Anselem and Nwoha (2021), e-governance is a unification of information and communication technologies (ICT) in all the operations to augment the potential of the government to satisfy the requirements of the local public. Additionally, it is a networked system where residents can communicate with the government and receive enhanced services via electronic applications (Ezeobebe, Anselem & Nwoha, 2021). E-governance, according to Almutairi, Thurasamy, and Yeap (2020), is the process of providing people or the general public with information and services through digital technology or electronic means.

E-governance according to El-Amrani and Louhmadi (2019) is a system of using modern information and communication technologies, and the internet as a tool for ensuring the effective functioning of all state agencies. E-governance, according to Omebe (2019), is the use of information and communication technology for transactions, information sharing, and service delivery that is both effective and efficient. According to Abah and Nwokwu (2019), e-governance helps governments make service delivery more effective, adaptable, lucrative, and competitive. Furthermore, e-governance describes how government organizations use information technologies (like the Internet, the World Wide Web, and mobile computing) to change how they interact with businesses, citizens, other government agencies, and other government sectors (Chukwuemeka, Okeke & Onwuchekwa, 2018). It is also the use of electronic devices in public sector to transform their operations for quality service delivery (Chukwuemeka, Okeke & Onwuchekwa 2018). Lawan and Muhammad (2018) claimed that e-governance, which includes e-services like e-tax systems, e-registration, and e-payment systems, among others, is a process of reforming how managements operate, share information, engage people, and provide services to internal and external clients for the benefit of the public.

The term "e-governance" refers to the use of contemporary technology to improve service delivery by promoting communication between the public and the government. Olalekan and Oludare (2017) supported this by claiming that e-governance encourages engagement and communication between the public and government organizations. E-governance, according to Chukwuemeka, Ubochi, and Okechukwu (2017), is the delivery of information services or goods by and from governmental organizations via electronic means at any time and location. Mohamed (2017) opined that e-governance is the use of ICT to assist in the administration or management of government affairs.

However, within the context of this study, e-governance simply refers to the successful adoption and utilization of ICT facilities and services within government Ministries, Departments and Agencies such as Nigerian College of Aviation Technology in view of providing effective and efficient public services such as online students' registration and payment.

Determinants of ICT (E-governance) Utilization

According to the UTAUT theoretical model, behavioral intention determines how technology is actually used. Four important constructs—performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions—have a direct impact on the anticipated likelihood of adopting the technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Zhang & Mao, 2020).

Performance Expectancy

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According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), performance expectancy is the extent to which a person thinks that utilizing the system will enable him or her to achieve improvements in job performance. Performance expectancy is the factor that most significantly influences an individual's propensity to use information systems, claim Venkatesh et al. (2003). It has a positive influence on behavioural intention according to previous studies. In other words, the higher the level of a user's confidence that e-government system can improve their performance, the higher the intention to use the e-government. The measurement of Performance expectancy is based on the benefits of e-government services, such as: time-saving, cost-saving and effort, ease of communication with government, improve service delivery and by enabling equal opportunities for citizens to carry out their businesses with government.

Effort Expectancy

Venkatesh et al. (2003) defines effort expectation as the degree of convenience associated with utilizing a particular system. Cimperman et al. (2016) state that PEOU, complexity, and ease of use are the antecedents of EE. The effect of the construct becomes non-significant after extended usage of technology (Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008; Chauhan & Jaiswal, 2016).

Social Influence

According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), social influence is the extent to which a person feels that other significant individuals think they ought to utilize the new system. When technology use is required, social influence has a big impact (Venkatesh et al., 2003). According to Venkatesh and Davis (2000), people may utilize technology in a mandated environment out of a need for conformity rather than out of personal desire. This could account for the construct's uneven influence across additional model validation investigations (Chauhan & Jaiswal, 2016; Zhou, Lu & Wang, 2010).

To Aneke Bakht and Desta (2019) social conditions also have a strong positive influence on the tendencies of an individual to adopt the use of an information system. Social influence simply refers to the tendencies that families and friends have the capacity to influence the adoption and utilization of an information system; be it positively or negatively.

Facilitating Conditions

According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), facilitating conditions are the extent to which a person thinks that there are institutions and technological infrastructure in place to enable system use. Intention to use is directly positively impacted by facilitating situations, although this effect is no longer substantial after the first usage. According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), the model suggests that conducive factors have a direct and substantial impact on use behavior.

Facilitating conditions is basically measured by the ability to access required e-government resources, and also to gain knowledge, and the necessary support needed to effectively utilize e-governance services. These determinants, measure, to a large extent, the degree of an individual's intention to utilize e-governance services in view of improving effective public service delivery.

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Empirical Review

The essence of reviewing previous studies is to identify the prevailing empirical, theoretical, and methodological gaps that may exist in the relationship between the core variables of the study; Information and Communication Technology measured by electronic governance and organizational performance measured by public service delivery as measures.

Francis, Francis and Ibiang (2023) investigated the possible relationship between public accountability and e-governance in Nigeria's Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The primary focus of the study is the analysis of previously published material that has been gathered through the use of secondary sources. Content analysis was employed in the analysis of the gathered secondary data. The study found that through enhancing transparency, citizen participation, effective service delivery, record-keeping, and real-time reporting of government actions, e-governance has the potential to improve public accountability in Nigeria, particularly in FIRS. The research findings indicate that several obstacles hinder the efficient implementation of e-governance, such as insufficient infrastructure, insufficient knowledge and skills, reluctance to adapt, and restricted financial means. The study suggested that in order to overcome the obstacles to the adoption and use of e-governance, policymakers should make investments in ICT infrastructure, develop human resources, and encourage an open and accountable culture within the public sector.

The study's concentration on previously published works and the lack of primary data from Nigeria are its main limitations. The study focused on accountability as a byproduct of high-quality service delivery rather than gathering and using primary data from surveys, interviews, and case studies to offer more context-specific insights into the relationship between e-governance and service delivery. The study did not offer any empirical support for the hypothesis that the variables under investigation are related.

Nnaji and Nri (2022) examined the link between electronic governance (E-Governance) and public sector service delivery (PSSD) from selected government ministries and departments. Descriptive statistics were used in the study to determine the impact of E-Gov on efficient service delivery in the chosen MDAs in the southern states as well as potential obstacles to E-Gov implementation in the research region. Questionnaire was utilized as the primary means of data collection, and the Special Package on Social Sciences (SPSS) was utilized for analysis of variance. The findings show that, among other things, a lack of sufficient E-Gov facilities, inadequate money, a lack of E-Gov capacity building, and inadequate access to internet services in government offices are the main reasons why the majority of government employees struggle with PSSD. The study suggested that in order to address the challenges associated with E-Gov policy and guarantee timely, high-quality, and outcome-oriented PSSD across government agencies and establishments, new E-Gov service reforms (EGSRs) should be adequately enabled financially through a sustainable e-governance impact assessment (SEGIA) model. The sample size employed is insufficient to draw firm conclusions on how e-governance affects the service delivery that is the subject of the study. Important informants who can provide insightful information about the relationships between the variables under investigation were not taken into account in this study.

Macdonald, Nnaji and David (2022) assessed the effects of e-governance and its application by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) during the 2019 general election in Nigeria. The study is primarily focused on the examination of existing literature collected via the use of secondary data. Primary data collected from the electorates were not statistically analysed. Content analysis was used to analyse the secondary data collected. The study found out that e-governance was not properly applied to

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service delivery during the 2019 election. This lack of effective application is evident in the rigging of the election in that year. The study makes several recommendations, one of which is that the federal government immediately guarantee the strict implementation of e-governance and contemporary technology in the conduct of all next elections in Nigeria; otherwise, the election ought to be declared invalid. In accordance with worldwide best practices, the government should guarantee that card readers and other electoral equipment are of the highest caliber. Among other things, this will stop election outcomes from being manipulated and rigged.

The study's concentration on previously published works and the lack of primary data from Nigeria are its main limitations. In order to provide further context-specific insights into the relationship between e-governance and service delivery, the study did not additionally involve the collecting and utilization of primary data, such as surveys, interviews, and case studies.

By evaluating the role of stakeholders in the implementation of e-governance for improved public service delivery in Nigeria, Dahiru, Yusuf, and Yerima (2022) investigated the relationship between e-governance and service delivery in that country. A correlation research design was employed for the study. The study's population consists of 100 members of the general public who employ any form of e-governance to perform public service in Nigeria, as well as a few chosen federal government agencies that comply with e-governance. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to choose 56 participants for the investigation. For the study, secondary data from statistical abstracts as well as primary data obtained through questionnaires were used. The data was analysed using both inferential statistics (Pearson correlation and multiple regression) and descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation). By the research findings, e-governance works well to improve services when stakeholders are involved. The study also shows that efficient communication and organizational abilities are critical to the establishment of e-governance in Nigeria. The study also shows that efficient communication and organizational abilities are critical to the establishment of e-governance in Nigeria.

The sample size used is inadequate to make a conclusive generalization. The study also did not examine the different dimensions of e-governance that are considered important for a successful implementation and utilization of e-governance for an enhanced service delivery. As such, it does not reflect the true state of the relationship between e-governance and service delivery in the area under study. The study did not adopt the use of advanced and sophisticated statistical tools such as Multiple Regression via the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) in the analysis of its data.

Ogu and Chukwurah (2022) investigated the relationship between e-governance and service delivery in Anambra State civil service, Nigeria between 2018 to 2022. The survey research design was adapted for the study. Using Krejcie and Morgan's sample size determination table, a sample size of 361 employees was selected from the 6,955 employees in the Anambra State Civil Service that made up the study's population. A questionnaire was employed as the data collection tool. The frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used to assess the data that were gathered. Among other things, the study's conclusions showed how heavily the Anambra State Civil Service uses e-governance in the provision of public services. Additionally, it was discovered that the Anambra State Civil Service's public service delivery has benefited from the implementation of e-governance. The Anambra State Civil Service should, among other things, regularly train and retrain its employees on information and web development technologies through yearly seminars, workshops, and conferences in order to keep them informed about

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the latest developments in the field of e-governance application for service delivery. The findings led to the formulation of these recommendations. The various facets of e-governance that are thought to be crucial for its effective deployment and application in order to improve service delivery were not covered in the study. The sample size used is inadequate to make a conclusive and generalized statement of the true picture of the effect of e-governance on service delivery. As such, it does not reflect the true state of the relationship between e-governance and service delivery in the area under study.

From the examination of previous studies, it is evident that there still exists a paucity, a lacuna and empirical gap on the issue of the successful adoption and utilization of ICT particularly in the form of e-governance in Nigerian public organizations such as NCAT in view of improving its performance in the form of public service delivery.

Theoretically, there is also a lack of empirical evidence on the application of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Utilization of Technology in Nigerian public organizations in Kaduna despite being the first to adopt the use of e-governance and open governance in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The study is underpinned by Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). The introduction and advancement in ICT have, over the years, drastically changed the way businesses are conducted in public sectors. The application of technologies in public organizations has tremendously redefined communication within and outside organizations in view of ensuing higher employee and organizational performance, as well as public service delivery (Marikyan, & Papagiannidis, 2023; Papagiannidis & Marikyan, 2020). However, in order to enjoy the benefits attached to the utilization of technologies, organizations are compelled to make huge investments in ICT. These huge investments do not, however, guarantee successful improvement in the performance and wellbeing of the organization. Market research has shown that the adoption of new technologies only brings about a success rate of 30% on return on investment, in other words, it only improves organizational performance by about 30% (Marikyan, & Papagiannidis, 2023). Examining the consequences of the poor adoption and utilization of ICT on organizational performance remains one of the major gaps in the area of literature on information system (Marikyan, & Papagiannidis, 2023).

Research in the area of adoption and utilization of new technologies have been the major focus of both public and private sectors which has resulted in a substantial amount of empirical evidence over the years (Marikyan, & Papagiannidis, 2023). Difference theories on the variation of the intention to use technologies account for 40% of the predictability of the acceptance of technologies (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Venkatesh et al. (2003) set out to provide a thorough knowledge of technology acceptance by integrating significant aspects that predict behavioral intention and use in order to provide a coherent theory of technology acceptance. Finding theoretical and contextual similarities and differences between theories of technology acceptance originating from three distinct research streams—behavioral psychology, IS management, and social psychology—was the aim of an analysis of the foundational literature on the acceptance of information systems (IS) (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

According to the UTAUT theoretical model, behavioral intention determines how technology is actually used. Four important constructs—performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and

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facilitating conditions—have a direct impact on the anticipated likelihood of adopting the technology (Zhang & Mao, 2020; Venkatesh et al., 2003).

According to research, UTAUT has contributed to the literature in a number of ways (Zhang & Mao, 2020). UTAUT has a higher predictive power than the other models that look at technology use (Davis, 1993; Sheppard, Hartwick & Warshaw, 1988) because it shows that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions account for 70% of the variance in ICT user intention (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

Rationale for the adoption of the theory

The UTAUT model and its robust variations has been widely applied to technology adoption and use in several contexts. Its reliability has been consistently validated, confirming its generalizability and supporting the argument that it serves as a benchmark for studies on technology adoption and utilization. Thus, this paper proposes a simple model adapted from the UTAUT model. Each of the four constructs—performance expectation, effort expectation, social influence, and facilitating conditions—that are the fundamental determinants of behavioral intention are directly linked by the model to organizational success, or the provision of public services. Accordingly, successful public service delivery (PSD) will be the study's dependent variable, and performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social impact, and facilitating factors will be its independent variables.

The UTAUT model was chosen as the base theoretical model for this study because of its comprehensiveness and high explanatory power in comparison to other technology acceptance and use models. UTAUT model was adopted to determine and explain the effects of factors that influence the adoption and utilization of ICT in the form of e-governance services. The results of this study will help decision makers to gain a better understanding of the factors that determine the adoption and utilization of technology and technological facilities in view of improving public service delivery (Uchenna, 2020).

The poor state of adoption and utilization of e-governance in improving public service delivery in Nigeria necessitate this study, hence the adoption and utilization of a more suitable theory that inadvertently captures all its underlying variables. Thus, this study covers this underlying literature gap by examining all the core-four-determinants of human behavioral intention as proposed in UTAUT. This will help to provide strong empirical evidence as to the effect of performance effort, expectancy effort, social influence and facilitating conditions on effective public service delivery in Nigerian College of Aviation Technology (NCAT) Zaria.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive survey research design. This design is considered most suitable because it enables the study to collect first-hand, factual, and reliable data from the actual respondents under study (Cresswell & Cresswell, 2018). The population of the study comprises 820 staff members at NCAT Zaria, out of which a sample of 350 participants was determined using the Yamane (1967) formula for determining sample size. Simple Random Sampling Technique was used in randomly selecting and administering the self-developed and administered close-ended questionnaire. The questionnaire was rated using Rensis Likert scale ranging from strongly agreed to strongly disagree. The data collection instrument was personally administered by the researchers with the help of two research assistants within the period of five working days. Multiple Regression statistical tool through the aid of Statistic Package for the Social

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Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 was used in testing the hypotheses of the study and also analyzing the primary data collected.

Presentation of Results

The descriptive analysis was conducted through the use of mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses testing was conducted through the use of Multiple Regression via the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 after which appropriate interpretations were made.

Descriptive analysis

Research Question 1

To what extent does performance expectancy affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?

This research question was answered through the aid of mean and standard deviation via the aid of SPSS 26.0.

Table 1: Employees' perception on Performance Expectancy

S/N	Performance Expectancy	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Using e-government services enables me to accomplish my needs from the public sector more quickly and more efficiently	3.92	.621	Agreed
2	Using the e-government services increases the equity between all citizens	3.77	.660	Agreed
3	Using e-government services would save citizens' time	4.02	.575	Agreed
4	Using the e-government services increases the quality of services	3.84	.682	Agreed

Source: Researcher Computation (2025)

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation) for four survey items related to the perceived benefits of using e-government services. The mean values for all four statements range from 3.77 to 4.02. This indicates that, on average, respondents tend to agree or strongly agree that using e-government services offers significant benefits in terms of efficiency, equity, time-saving, and service quality. The responses are generally positive. The data suggests a strong positive perception of e-government services among the respondents, particularly concerning their ability to save time and improve efficiency. While still positive, the perceived impact on equity and overall service quality shows slightly less unanimous agreement, indicating areas where perception might be more varied or where the actual impact might be less consistently felt or observed. The low standard deviations for most items highlight a general consensus on these perceived benefits.

Research Question 2

To what extent does effort expectancy affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?

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This research question was answered through the aid of mean and standard deviation via the aid of SPSS 26.0.

Table 2: Employees’ perception on Effort Expectancy

S/N	Effort Expectancy	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Learning to use the e-government services system is easy	3.35	.897	Agreed
2	Using the e-government services system is easy	3.40	.914	Agreed
3	It is easy for me to become skillful at using the e-government services system	3.44	.893	Agreed
4	By using the e-government system, I am able to get government services easily	3.64	.830	Agreed

Source: Researcher Computation (2025)

The mean values for these four statements range from 3.35 to 3.64. This suggests that while respondents generally perceive e-government services as moderately easy to learn and use, and helpful for accessing services easily, the level of agreement is not as strong or enthusiastic as the previous table (which showed means closer to 4.0). There's a notable spread in opinions, as indicated by the relatively higher standard deviations compared to the previous table. The data concerning effort expectancy for e-government services indicates a generally neutral to moderately positive perception. While respondents agree that they can eventually get services easily through the system, there is considerable variability and less strong agreement regarding the inherent ease of learning and using the system itself. This suggests that while the benefits of access are recognized, there might still be some usability challenges or a learning curve that affects different users in different ways.

Research Question 3

To what extent does social influence affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?

This research question was answered through the aid of mean and standard deviation via the aid of SPSS 26.0.

Table 3: Employees’ perception on Social Influence

S/N	Social Influence	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	People who are important to me think that I should use e-government services.	3.57	1.382	Agreed
2	People who influence my behaviour think I should use the e-government services	3.84	1.059	Agreed
3	I would use e-government services if my friends and colleagues used them	3.66	1.174	Agreed
4	Government sectors encourage citizens to use the e-government services	3.57	1.266	Agreed

Source: Researcher Computation (2025)

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The mean values for these four statements range from 3.57 to 3.84. This indicates that respondents perceive a moderate level of social influence encouraging the use of e-government services. The data suggests that while, on average, there's a moderate perception of social influence promoting e-government services, this influence is highly varied across the respondent base. There is no widespread, uniform social pressure or encouragement perceived by all citizens. This could indicate a challenge in leveraging social influence to drive e-government adoption without understanding the specific dynamics within different community segments.

Research Question 4

To what extent does facilitating conditions affect public service delivery in NCAT Zaria?

This research question was answered through the aid of mean and standard deviation via the aid of SPSS 26.0.

Table 4: Employees' perception on facilitating conditions

S/N	Facilitating Conditions	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	I have the resources necessary to use e-government services	3.67	.742	Agreed
2	I have the knowledge necessary to use e-government services	3.80	.716	Agreed
3	There is a specific person or group available for assistance with any technical problem I may encounter	3.80	.725	Agreed
4	There is supportive government policy to support the utilization of e-government services.	3.67	.747	Agreed

Source: Researcher Computation (2025)

The mean values for these four statements range from 3.67 to 3.80. This indicates that, on average, respondents perceive that facilitating conditions are moderately present and supportive for using e-government services. The data on Facilitating Conditions paints a relatively positive and consistent picture. Respondents generally agree that they have the necessary resources and knowledge to use e-government services, and importantly, they perceive that technical assistance is available and that supportive government policies exist. The low standard deviations across all items highlight a good level of consensus among the surveyed population regarding these facilitating factors. This suggests that the foundational elements enabling e-government service use are largely in place and recognized by citizens, which is a strong positive for fostering adoption.

Hypotheses Testing

Table 5: Correlation Coefficient (Coefficients^a)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	1.659	.204		8.139	.000
Performance Expectancy	.172	.066	.166	2.609	.009

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Effort Expectancy	.152	.037	.224	4.139	.000
Social Influence	.064	.038	.084	1.676	.095
Facilitating Conditions	.215	.052	.248	4.101	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Effective Public Service Delivery

Source: SPSS Output 2025

The result of the hypotheses testing are better examined under discussion of findings.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis of the primary data collected, it was found that:

The findings revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between performance expectancy and effective public service delivery ($p < 0.05$; $t=2.609$; $sig=0.009$), indicating that staff members believe using ICT enhances their ability to perform their duties effectively. This is in line with the study of Francis, Francis and Ibiang (2023) who found in their study that performance expectancy enhances public service delivery through enhancing transparency, citizen participation, effective service delivery, record-keeping, and real-time reporting of government actions.

The study also found out that effort expectancy was found to positively and significantly influence effective public service delivery ($p < 0.05$; $t=4.139$; $sig=0.000$). This tallies with the study of Macdonald, Nnaji and David (2022) who found out that the lack of technical know-how and capability are some of the factors militating against the effective functioning of INEC during elections. In agreement, Dahiru, Yusuf, and Yerima (2022) revealed that efficient communication and organizational abilities are critical to the establishment of e-governance for effective public service delivery in Nigeria. In furtherance, Francis, Francis and Ibiang (2023) added that insufficient knowledge and skills on how to effectively utilize e-governance services are some of the hindrances to effective public service delivery in Nigeria. As such, Ogu and Chukwurah (2022) recommended that government should regularly train and retrain its employees on information and web development technologies through yearly seminars, workshops, and conferences in order to keep them informed about the latest developments in the field of e-governance application for service delivery.

On the other hand, the study found out that social influence showed a positive but insignificant relationship with effective public service delivery ($p > 0.05$; $t=1.676$; $sig=0.095$), suggesting that peer perceptions may not significantly affect ICT utilization in this context. This is in agreement with Chauhan and Jaiswal (2016) who revealed that social influence accounts for uneven effect across cultures as such need culture-sensitive validation. Venkatesh and Davis (2000) further added that employees usually utilize technological facilities in a mandated environment in other to conform to organizational demand rather than out of personal desire, as such, its influence may differ.

The study further found out that Facilitating conditions were also positively and significantly correlated with effective public service delivery ($p < 0.05$; $t=4.101$; $sig=0.000$), underscoring the importance of adequate resources and support. This corroborate the study of Nnaji and Nri (2022) who found out that a lack of sufficient E-Gov facilities, inadequate money, a lack of E-Gov capacity building, and inadequate access to internet services in government offices are the main reasons why the majority of government employees struggle with providing effective public services. Collaborating this, Francis, Francis and Ibiang (2023) also revealed in their study that insufficient infrastructure, insufficient knowledge and skills,

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reluctance to adapt, and restricted financial means are some of the factors militating against effective public service delivery in Nigeria.

The results of this study align with existing literature that emphasizes the critical role of ICT in improving educational outcomes and organizational performance (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023). Specifically, the findings suggest that NCAT's management should prioritize the training of staff in ICT utilization and create a supportive environment that fosters the effective use of technology. This will not only enhance public service delivery but also ensure that NCAT remains a leader in aviation education.

Conclusion

The integration of ICT in the operations of the Nigerian College of Aviation Technology has the potential to significantly enhance public service delivery. The study concluded that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence have a positive and significant effect on public service delivery in NCAT, while social influence has a positive but insignificant effect on public service delivery. Thus, by focusing on performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and facilitating conditions, NCAT can improve its organizational performance and better serve its students and the aviation sector.

Recommendations

To maximize the benefits of ICT in aviation education, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Implement comprehensive training programs for staff on the effective use of ICT tools in delivering services.
- ii. Establish a framework for continuous evaluation and improvement of ICT infrastructure at NCAT.
- iii. Foster a culture of innovation and collaboration among staff to encourage the adoption of e-governance practices.
- iv. Development and implementation of policies and programmes that will ensure mandatory utilization of e-governance tools and services.

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